

INDUSTRIAL CHATBOT DESIGN and OPTIMIZATION USING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS and MODERN NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract— Rapid developments in the field of deep learning have led to the emergence of large language models, which have played a seminal role in the understanding and processing of natural language. Such models are characterized by their capacity to analyze the structural complexity of language and generate human-like responses. They have been successful in applications where humans interact, such as chatbots. However, the high licensing fees and intensive hardware requirements of commercial language models have increased interest in open-source solutions. In this study, open-source models such as DeepSeek-R1 and LLaMA 3.1 are used to achieve high throughput with lower resource requirements. In order to improve the performance of open-source language models, a fine-tuning process is performed using the LoRA method. In addition, a knowledge retrieval based architecture is integrated to further improve the performance of the model. The models in this system are compared with the Claude 3.7 commercial model. Two separate datasets based on ChatGPT and Gemini are used for the comparison tests. The results show that low-parameter, open-source models, with appropriate fine-tuning and knowledge retrieval support, can compete with commercial large-scale models. As a result of this study, open-source models and retrieval augmented generation stand out as an effective alternative in hardware-constrained environments and with limited resources.

Keywords—Large Language Models, Retrieval Augmented Generation, Embedding, Vector Database, Fine Tuning

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies has paved the way for the emergence of new and powerful methods aimed at successfully applied in many fields such as image processing, autonomous vehicles, and natural language processing [1]

Natural language processing technologies offer the ability to generate precise and consistent responses by analyzing the intricate structure of human language. The application of deep learning techniques in the field of natural language processing, especially with the emergence of transformer-based models, enables the creation of systems that deeply understand the complex structure of language. Initially, the scope of natural

language processing was generally limited to narrow tasks such as simply classifying texts and analyzing their emotional content. However, thanks to ChatGPT and similar large language models, the development of systems with in-depth contextual understanding that can answer much more complex questions has been made possible [2]. Large language models are increasing efficiency across various sectors, from engineering to entertainment, thanks to their boundary-pushing performance. As a result, large companies worldwide have started investing heavily in the development of large language models, and similarly, academics have begun to focus on detailed research and development activities in this area. Every year, new developments emerge in different transformer architectures, training strategies, and fine-tuning techniques [3].

In the modern era, the error rate of people working on complex and large systems, such as in the field of engineering, must be extremely low. In fields such as aviation, automotive, critical infrastructure, chemistry, and defense, even seemingly small mistakes can lead to severe consequences. In this process, individuals working in different sectors were using word-based search methods, which are traditional information access methods, to access reliable information. However, these methods are limited in understanding highly complex contexts, so they cannot always successfully provide reliable information. In order to solve these problems, large language models stand out in many sectors due to their high performance. However, there are still some risks in critical sectors.

The information retrieval technique emerges as a method designed to overcome the current challenges related to the reliability and accuracy of large language models. This method feeds language models with reference-based and reliable sources. In this way, language models can provide accurate responses to users. Additionally, the model's ability to generate language and its competence in utilizing real-time information are being developed [4]. The semantic search method is used in the process of the information retrieval technique. In the semantic search technique, documents and user requests are digitized using mathematical algorithms. By using similar algorithms among numerical contexts, the most accurate

information is obtained. However, there are many technical terms in engineering documents. In some cases, the technical explanation in the texts cannot be matched with the question asked by the users with a high success rate. For this reason, incorrect information may be conveyed to the user by the BDM.

Large language models are used by users in two ways. BDM services are activated either by using the model service [5] or by running open-source language models [6] on their own networks. Some companies do not want to operate outside of a closed and secure network in areas requiring security and data privacy. Therefore, completely local network deployments need to be preferred. However, high-performance hardware systems are required for the efficient use of BDMS. Another problem is that BDMs are trained to address a wide audience using data from different sources such as the internet, books, and social media. Therefore, there is a problem with general models producing superficial responses in applications that require depth of knowledge. To overcome this problem, fine-tuning methods are used. The process of further training models that have been trained with large datasets on a smaller dataset for a specific task is called fine-tuning. Thus, BDMs can produce consistent responses by better understanding the terminology and semantic relationships specific to that field [7].

In this study, an information retrieval-based architectural structure is being designed to solve the problems mentioned. To implement this architectural design, infrastructure with 40 gigabytes of graphics processing power using A100 NVIDIA hardware is employed. Two large language models have been selected for use within this architectural structure. In order for the selected language models to respond contextually better, a fine-tuning training process will take place. For the fine-tuning method, question-answer pairs will be synthetically generated within the scope of systems engineering using model service services for the DL models. In order to make the information retrieval process more efficient, there are input engineering processes. Thus, the user's question is further detailed, aiming to extract accurate information from the document. Another improvement made in the information retrieval process is the hybrid search method. With this approach model, the aim is to increase accuracy in information retrieval through both word-based search and semantic search. Additionally, the information retrieved for the most accurate documents is evaluated using re-ranking models by the language model. Thus, matching the user's question with the most relevant answers will be more efficient. Since systems engineering answers are a critical area, the answers produced by the fine-tuned language model are asked again to the language model that has undergone fine-tuning. The inconsistency between the user's question and the language model's output is being checked. Thanks to these improvements, both increasing user satisfaction and reducing the level of hallucination are aimed. This study has shown that in applications conducted with limited hardware and resources, open-source models and knowledge retrieval-based solutions offer an effective and sustainable alternative.

II. BACKGROUND

Chatbot applications are generally developed using three different methods: (1) using a word-based approach, (2) using a vector search-based approach, and (3) using only large language

models. In addition, fine-tuning methods, prompt engineering, and reordering methods are also used to increase the efficiency of natural language processing processes. Unfortunately, the aforementioned studies are mostly used separately. The development of these different components through end-to-end integration has been limited. Furthermore, studies are being conducted without considering resource constraints. This study aims to combine these components into a single architectural structure.

A. Knowledge Retrieval Augmented LLMs (RAG)

Word-based approaches were the first to be developed in natural language processing studies. With the emergence of large language models, RAG architectures have become prominent. This method feeds language models with reference-based, reliable sources. This allows language models to provide accurate responses to users [4].

B. Domain Adaptation via Fine-Tuning and Synthetic Dataset

When training large language models, they are generated using datasets with general topics. Consequently, they exhibit poor performance when answering questions specific to a specific domain. Fine-tuning methods such as LoRA/PEFT are used to address this problem [8]. Due to the lack of real datasets, high-quality, suitable datasets are synthetically generated to perform fine-tuning.

C. Prompt Engineering and Query Expansion for Retrieval Quality

For large language models, the right question is crucial for performance. Refining, parsing, and granularizing the query increases the accuracy of information retrieval processes [9].

D. Hybrid Search and Learning to Rank Re-Ranking

The combined use of word-based and mathematical search methods improves performance. Responses generated through the retrieval method are subsequently re-ranked using a cross-encoder, ensuring that the most relevant results are placed at the forefront [10].

E. Hallucination Mitigation and Answer Verification

Evidence-based production, consistency checks, evaluation, and confirmatory methods are used for hallucination reduction. In critical situations, mechanisms that verify the relevance of the response to both the source text and the question strengthen reliability.

F. Gap Analysis

The developed domain-based application addresses three gaps in systems engineering. (1) End-to-end architectures that combine RAG, fine-tuning, hybrid search, and verification components and are compatible with resource-constrained hardware are scarce. (2) Training language models with general datasets leads to a knowledge gap in the systems engineering domain. (3) Quantitative evaluations integrated with re-ranker and system engineering are limited.

G. Our Contribution

This study aims to address the identified gaps using the Fetch, Fit, and Verify framework. Hybrid search and reordering are used for accurate retrieval. The adaptation step utilizes a

parameter-efficient adaptation (fine-tune) method implemented on a synthetic dataset. The RAGAS framework is used for post-retrieval verification. This pipeline enables the development of an efficient end-to-end solution in systems engineering.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Parameter Efficient Fine Tuning

Both supervised and self-supervised learning methods are used to create large language models. To ensure that the model learns within a designated domain, fine-tuning is carried out after training. Due to large datasets, high human demands, and the requirement for high-performance hardware infrastructures, fine-tuning every BDM parameter is difficult. The effectiveness of parameter-efficient fine-tuning techniques (PEFT), which allow for fine-tuning specific parameters rather than the entire model parameters, was examined [11]. The Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) Method is one of the most commonly used PEFT techniques. LoRA technique was introduced in a study focusing on parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods [12]. This technique keeps the weights of the large language model, which has completed its training process, fixed. By adding low-level matrices to the transformer layer, both the number of parameters that need to be trained and the GPU memory requirements are reduced. The weights of the parameters of the pre-trained $W_0 \in R^{d \times k}$ large language model is frozen. Two low-dimensional matrices $A \in R^{r \times k}$ and $B \in R^{d \times r}$ are defined. While matrix A is formed using random values based on a normal distribution, matrix B is adjusted so that its values are zero. Additionally, for the LoRA method to work correctly, the value of r must be smaller than the values of d and k. The fundamental working principle of this technique involves applying matrix multiplication for the B and A matrices to add the weights to the frozen matrix.

B. The Unsloth

The Unsloth platform, created by Unsloth AI, seeks to enhance the efficiency and usability of fine-tuning techniques in artificial intelligence (AI). It provides an expedited training procedure and rapid answers relative to alternative approaches, exhibiting effective performance in training extensive datasets and lengthy sentence [13]. This study was conducted by leasing an NVIDIA A100 40GB GPU through Google Colab, which served as the main computational environment. The platform's open-source architecture, hardware compatibility, and diverse optimization methods render it appropriate for refining the DeepSeek – R1 and Llama 3.1 models. The platform's open-source architecture, hardware compatibility, and diverse optimization methods render it an invaluable resource for improving the performance of transformer-based models.

Hyperparameter selection is crucial to deep learning model training with artificial neural networks. Hyperparameters control massive language model learning and data adaptation. This study uses LoRA to fine-tune DeepSeek-R1 and Llama 3.1 hyperparameters. First, the "r" parameter determines low-dimensional matrix size. This parameter facilitates smarter model parameter use while retaining learning potential. Alpha regulates adaption layer data output scale. The target modules parameter determines which transforming model layers undergo low-dimensional adaptation. This makes attention fine-tuning

efficient and effective. The learning rate parameter controls model learning. Many supervised learning algorithms use it to predict how much the model's parameters will change during training.

These values were determined by comparing "r" and lora-alpha values, two crucial LoRA fine-tuning factors. The experiment used one model due to budget and resource constraints. Llama 3.1 was used to discover the best hyperparameter. The procedure of fine-tuning was tested with various hyperparameter values for 1000 steps. Figure 1 shows the train/loss graph analyzing "r" and alpha parameters with values of 8, 16, and 32. This graph shows how much the model decreases training error. The graph shows all combinations progressively decreasing from 2.5 to 0.8. The rankings of all combinations are 0–1. All combinations show similar trends and swings.

Fig. 1. Training Error Rate for Different Hyperparameter Values in the Fine-Tuning Process

See train/grad_norm graph in Figure 2. This graph identifies parameters with consistent gradient values and few fluctuations. A high level indicates overlearning, while a low one indicates inadequate learning. The necessary "r" and alpha pairings are (16,16) and (16,8).

Fig. 2. Gradient Ratio for Different Hyperparameter Values in the Fine-Tuning Process

The Unsloth framework's high-efficiency fine-tuning system suggests reference values. The "r" and alpha values are 16. To finish fine-tuning, the DeepSeek-R1 and Llama 3.1 models are trained for 1000 steps using the values in Table 3.7 and our experimental results. The learning rate and number of training phases in this study help language models learn efficiently and fairly. Both approaches reduce training loss after 1000 steps. Training loss starts at 2.5–3 and drops to 0.6–0.8 by the end. Table I shows the hyperparameter values used for fine-tuning.

TABLE I. HYPERPARAMETER VALUES USED IN THE FINE-TUNING PROCESS

Hyperparameters	Values
r	16
Alpha	16
Target Module	q_proj, k_proj, v_proj, o_proj, gate_proj, up_proj, ve down_proj
Learning Rate	2e-4

C. Fine Tuning Dataset

Instructions following big language models (LLMs) depend on the Alpaca structure as a required data structure. This study from Stanford University aims to make these models better at following directions by using a methodical data-format structure [14]. The command step, input section, and outcome component of the construction comprise three interrelated components. During the first part of the study, an average of 190 engineering concepts are created, and each subject has 218 question templates made for them. These models offer theoretical and pragmatic applications as well as knowledge about upcoming trends and issues related with pertinent concepts. Using question templates for every topic, the system generates questions then uses OpenAI's GPT-3.5-turbo model to offer answers via an API. To control model output, the system input is set with a segment length of 500 and a diversity hyperparameter value of 0.7. The model creates its outputs automatically in line with the format of the Alpaca dataset. The second phase consisted in a translating process to guarantee the data pool is not limited to Turkish. Following 76.23% of the 42,094 Turkish data set into English yields 74,178 data points for fine-tuning. However, semantic shifts were detected during this translation process. Therefore, all translated data was checked using Gemini Pro, and translations with semantic shifts were corrected. The aim is to enhance the model's performance while Alpaca style tailoring of BDMs is under progress.

D. Retrieval Augmented Generation Architecture

In this study, an architectural structure that produces answers to user queries using the document-based information access method is designed. This architectural structure is shown in Figure 1. The system uses the RAG methodology to gather data from external sources upon the submission of a user query. The system subsequently uses the fine-tuned LLM to communicate the response to the user. The system initiates by examining the user's inquiry pertaining to engineering. The optimized LLM executes input engineering to enhance the clarity of the inquiry. The refined inquiry is transmitted to a document scanning and information retrieval agent, which digitizes and incorporates terms into a vector database. The content most aligned with the user's request is identified through semantic and lexical search techniques. The optimized LLM produces two responses based on the user's inquiry and the most relevant information, which are assessed by the LLM and delivered to the user as a reply.

Fig. 3. Information Retrieval Based System Architecture Responding to User Queries

E. Retrieval Augmented Generation Generation

Using five internationally known English sources in system engineering—the Twelve System Engineering Roles, NASA Systems Engineering Handbook, INCOSE Systems Engineering Guidebook, INCOSE SE Handbook (2015 Edition), and HELIX System Engineering Report—this thesis centers on the development of a knowledge-based production solution. Over the course of their product life, these tools provide businesses thorough knowledge on key issues including planning, managing, developing, testing, and improving. Usually, a common solution development process is used to guarantee that the solution not only gives users information but also serves as a guide for company employees, so giving users dependable, context-oriented responses. The aim of the research is to provide field of systems engineering users with contextually relevant solutions.

F. Chunking

In AI-assisted information retrieval systems, it is essential to segment texts into coherent smaller pieces for effective digitization and storage in a vector database. This study employs the RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter class from the LangChain library for document segmentation [15]. Documents are segmented into units, each approximately 1000 characters long, with the final 50 characters of one unit overlapping with the initial 50 characters of the subsequent unit. This setup is anticipated to yield more precise responses to customers' inquiries and enhance overall efficiency.

G. Embedding System

Focusing on the creation of numerical representations of texts is essential for the proper functioning of information retrieval systems. Sentences, words, or subwords are transformed into vector space during this process. We call this process vectorization. Every word, sentence, and paragraph are quantitatively encoded based on its context within a multidimensional space during the vectorization process. The third iteration of the Jina vectorization model, comprising approximately 570 million parameters, was made publicly available [16]. 89 different language datasets have been used in the training process. Up to 8192 subword units of text can be entered into it. Comparative tests have shown that it is more efficient than other models used in open-source multilingual applications and commercial models such as OpenAI and Cohere. The transformer in this model has 24 layers in total. A particular adapter is activated to carry out the vectorization process based on the type of job. The average pooling technique is then used to convert the output into a fixed-size array. Because it supports the Turkish language, this paradigm was selected for our information retrieval-based chatbot.

H. Vector Database

Managing text, images, and similar data becomes more difficult as unstructured data grows in size. To get around this problem, vector databases are being investigated [17]. This study makes use of the Chroma database, which makes it possible to store high-dimensional data while maintaining its semantic integrity and facilitating quick and scalable querying. The vector database is closely related to the vectorization and document splitting processes [18]. Systems engineering-related documents are broken up into smaller sections and converted to digital format using the Jina vectorization model. When a user queries, the query sentence is vectorized once more using multidimensional and semantic features that are stored in the vector database. Using the best similarity metrics, this procedure finds the text segments in the vector database that are most pertinent to the user query.

I. Intelligent Query Validation and Routing Architecture

The precision of responses generated by big language models relies on the accurate identification of the contextual meaning of user prompts. In specialized systems, such as those in engineering, the prompt removal of extraneous content is crucial for the efficient utilization of model resources and the dependability of outputs. This study proposes a two-stage filtering and validation method to assess the correlation between user inputs and the engineering discipline. Initially, content is efficiently and economically screened utilizing an extensive list of prohibitive terms pertaining to non-engineering subjects. This index encompasses a diverse array of non-engineering disciplines, spanning from everyday life to politics. In the second phase, content that successfully undergoes initial screening but retains ambiguity in its relationship is subjected to meticulous content analysis utilizing refined large language models, and the technical context is validated. Consequently, although the system's performance and accuracy are improved, resource utilization is also maximized.

J. Prompt Engineering

Prompt engineering is a technique that structures user inputs to guarantee that big language models yield anticipated outputs. It enhances model efficiency without necessitating retraining and provides considerable benefits, particularly in specialized tasks and constrained data scenarios. Twenty-six guiding principles to enhance the communicative efficacy of large language models were assembled [19]. Open-source and commercial models are employed to assess the efficacy of these principles. The research indicated that the suggested principles enhance both the quality and precision of the model's replies. This study provides a reference for enhancing input through three templates that demonstrate effective outcomes in models with 8 billion parameters. The initial stage is to identify the language of the user's original request, which is essential for ensuring good communication with the language model. This strategy improves accuracy, semantic coherence, and content consistency of outputs since big language models are predominantly trained on English data and engineering resources are utilized in English. The input is enhanced via comprehensive simplification, task segmentation, and illustrative coaching phases. Deep simplification clarifies technical stuff and prompts the model to function as an educator by offering contextual information. Task decomposition disaggregates input into sub-tasks to enhance efficiency in outcomes. Ultimately, instances analogous to the intended answer type are incorporated into the input using the example-based guidance approach. This input engineering enables the model to assess the context with greater precision and deliver a more comprehensive and accurate response to the user's inquiry.

K. Search Approaches in Information Retrieval Based Systems

In natural language processing, traditional word-based search methods, despite achieving high F1 scores [20], struggle with deep semantic understanding, synonym differentiation, and complex sentence structures. To overcome these limitations, deep learning-powered semantic vector search methods position documents in multilayered vector spaces and utilize metrics such as cosine similarity to analyze semantic similarities [21]. While these semantic methods effectively handle conceptual meaning, they sometimes neglect key terms. To address these limitations, a hybrid search model combining both word-based and semantic searches has been developed. This hybrid approach optimizes information retrieval and reliability, as demonstrated in a recent study [10]. In this thesis, the hybrid model utilizes an 80% weighting for semantic searches and 20% for word-based searches, balancing semantic depth with keyword precision, thus offering comprehensive and meaningful search outcomes.

L. Re-ranking Method Based on Semantic Coherence

When someone asks a question, the hybrid search gives us a certain set of information. We make our finely calibrated models work better by assessing and ranking the information before we get it. We apply the ColBERTv2 model to make the contextual similarity between queries and retrieved material more accurate. The best thing about this approach is that it can look at both queries and documents in more than one way, instead of just one overall one. This way, semantic relationships

that are missed in the first stage can be found in later stages, and paragraphs that are more meaningful can be given a higher rank. ColBERTv2's late interaction technique increases document ranking by better understanding the context. It also makes the most of resources by using compression and supervised learning approaches [22].

M. Response Generation Process with Customized Big Language Models

This project constructs a structured production function to output Turkish responses from a language model for novice systems engineers. This process begins with defining the model's system role. Comments are detailed, varied, and motivating. The input generation method splits the query and language model system information into units and sends them to the model's hardware environment. Hyperparameter values are empirically investigated to ensure large language models provide accurate and high-performance responses. The parameters, testing intervals, and increments are in Table II. Parameter ranges were based on literature values. Ten DeepSeek-R1 and Llama 3.1 model questions were fine-tuned for each parameter value. Three system engineers examined language model responses. At low temperatures, outputs were predictable and sometimes incomplete. At high temperatures, they produced unnecessary and diverse responses. At low top_p numbers, repetitive responses reduced answer diversity. Top_p values over 1 produced inaccurate data. In the 1–1.2 range, the repetition penalty parameter reduced text redundancy and increased information density.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTED RANGES OF HYPERPARAMETERS FOR LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL RESPONSE GENERATION

Hyperparameters	Tested Range	Increase Amount
Temperature	0.2 – 2.0	0.2 – 0.3
Top_p	0.2 – 2.0	0.2 – 0.3
Repetition Penalty	0.2 – 2.0	0.2 – 0.3

Table III shows the hyperparameter values we will use to generate the best language model responses for systems engineering. The minimum output length is 512 subunits, and the maximum is 4096 to provide complete responses. The model's temperature was calibrated to 50% to ensure more consistent and significant results. This limits the language model's originality. The top-p value was set at 90% to emphasize high-probability options. To avoid redundancy and generate more diverse information, a repetition penalty of 1.2 was added. These hyperparameter configurations improve model balance and significance.

TABLE III. HYPERPARAMETER VALUES ADJUSTED FOR RESPONSE GENERATION OF FINE-TUNED LANGUAGE MODELS

Hyperparameters	Values
Minimum Token Number	512
Maximum Token Number	4096
Temperature	%50

Hyperparameters	Values
Top_p	%90
Repetition Penalty	1.2

IV. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

In this study, two distinct reference datasets based on ChatGPT [23] and Gemini [24] were utilized to evaluate an AI-driven solution tailored for systems engineering. During testing, fine-tuned DeepSeek-R1 and LLaMA 3.1 models were compared with the commercial Claude 3.7 model, known for its security-oriented and controlled response generation [25]. Model outputs were assessed using the RAGAS evaluation framework across four metrics: response relevance, answer accuracy, information faithfulness, and factual correctness [26]. The first dataset, based on ChatGPT-o1, included 50 questions covering fundamental concepts and practical scenarios of systems engineering, providing balanced engineering content. Responses generated by ChatGPT-o1 served as reference answers for evaluating the fine-tuned DeepSeek-R1 and LLaMA 3.1 models, employing a knowledge-enhanced retrieval framework. The second dataset comprised an additional 50 questions designed around contemporary topics such as project management, collaboration, complexity, ethics, artificial intelligence, and sustainability. Responses from fine-tuned 8-billion-parameter DeepSeek-R1 and LLaMA 3.1 models were evaluated against answers provided by the Gemini 2.0 Flash model, emphasizing their ability to address modern challenges in systems engineering.

1) Response Relevance: This metric evaluates the semantic compatibility of the question and the answer. Answers that stray from the question's purpose and include unnecessary details receive lower scores. This metric is scored as 0 or 1. The calculation formula is shown in (1).

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{cosine similarity}(E_{gi}, E_o) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{E_{gi} \cdot E_o}{\|E_{gi}\| \cdot \|E_o\|} \quad (1)$$

Some abbreviations within the metric above are:

E_{gi} : Vectorized version of the i . AI question

E_o : Vectorized version of the user question

N : Number of artificial intelligence questions generated

2) Response Accuracy: This metric is used to analyze the degree to which our designed system aligns with the reference response. The resulting score is on a scale of 0 to 1. The response accuracy metric consists of two main components: semantic similarity and factual agreement. In the semantic similarity phase, the level of semantic similarity between the reference response and the system engineering chatbot is measured. In factual agreement, the level of compatibility between the model response and the information in the reference response is determined. The formula for semantic similarity is shown in (2), while the formula for factual agreement is shown in (3).

$$\cos \left(\vec{a}, \vec{r} \right) = \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{r}}{\|a\| \cdot \|r\|} \quad (2)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are as follows:

\rightarrow_a : Vectorized version of the expert's response

\rightarrow_r : Vectorized version of the reference response

$$\frac{TP}{(|TP| + 0.5 \times (|FP| + |FN|))} \quad (3)$$

Some abbreviations for the metric above are:

TP: Information found in both the expert response we developed and the reference response (True Positive)

FP: Information found only in the expert response but not in the reference response (False Positive)

FN: Information found in the reference response but not in the expert response (False Negative)

3) Faithfulness: This metric evaluates the contextual consistency of the expert's answer. In other words, it measures the correspondence between the expert's answer and the information in the external source. The calculation formula is shown in (4).

$$\frac{\text{Number of Arguments Supported}}{\text{Total Number of Arguments}} \quad (4)$$

4) Factual Consistency: This metric allows us to verify whether the information in the expert's answer is included in the reference answer. The primary purpose of this metric is to verify whether the expert's answers are derived from the reference answers.

Precision formula is shown in (5).

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5)$$

Recall formula is shown in (6).

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

F1 Score formula is shown (7).

$$\frac{2 \times \text{Accuracy} \times \text{Precision}}{\text{Accuracy} + \text{Precision}} \quad (7)$$

Here are some abbreviations for the metrics above:

TP: Number of claims included in the expert's answer but not referenced (True Positive)

FP = Number of claims included in the expert's answer but not referenced (False Positive)

FN = Number of claims included in the reference but not referenced (False Negative)

A. Results Obtained with ChatGPT Based Dataset

The test results based on the dataset created with ChatGPT are presented in Table 3. In these evaluations, the Claude 3.7 model demonstrated strong capability in generating semantically relevant responses, achieving an average response relevance score of 84.62. However, a faithfulness score of 0% indicates that Claude's answers lacked consistency with the reference data, suggesting its outputs should be carefully

considered in scenarios requiring contextual integrity. The fine-tuned DeepSeek-R1 model achieved a slightly higher average response relevance score of 84.69%, indicating strong semantic alignment with user queries. Additionally, it recorded 26.12% factual accuracy and 34.29% answer correctness, showing a higher degree of content consistency. Its faithfulness score of 8.03% demonstrates better adherence to contextual information compared to Claude. The fine-tuned LLaMA 3.1 model also performed well, with an 82.77% response relevance score, indicating a high degree of alignment between responses and questions. Although its 4.49% faithfulness score shows improvement over Claude, it still reveals room for growth in semantic accuracy. The model's factual accuracy (23.70%) and answer correctness (33.27%) also indicate its ability to generate contextually functional responses.

TABLE IV. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF DEEPSEEK-R1, LLAMA 3.1 AND CLAUDE 3.7 BASED ON THE CHATGPT-DERIVED EVALUATION SET

Test Type	RAG System Using DeepSeek- R1	RAG System Using Llama 3.1	Claude 3.7
Response Relevance	%84,69	%82,77	%84,62
Response Accuracy	%34,29	%33,27	%45,65
Faithfulness	%8,03	%4,49	%0
Factual Consistency	%26,12	%23,70	%33,14

B. Results Obtained with Gemini Based Dataset

The test results based on the dataset created with Gemini are presented in Table 4. In this evaluation, the Claude 3.7 model achieved a response relevance score of 84.18%, demonstrating its ability to generate semantically aligned responses. With an answer correctness score of 42.18%, the model showed that it could produce outputs grounded in a broad knowledge base. However, its faithfulness score of 2.00% suggests that the content does not always align adequately with the given context. The expert system developed using the DeepSeek-R1 model demonstrated a balanced and robust performance, achieving 79.39% in response relevance, 30.48% in answer correctness, and 18.14% in factual accuracy. Thanks to the domain-specific fine-tuning process based on the LoRA technique, this system exhibited strong adaptability in knowledge-driven tasks. The information retrieval-based system using the LLaMA 3.1 model achieved the highest response relevance score of 84.41%, indicating its capacity to deliver semantically coherent answers to user queries. Additionally, its answer correctness score of 31.01% and factual accuracy of 20.90% demonstrate that the model generates functionally reliable outputs not only in terms of form but also in terms of content accuracy.

TABLE V. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF DEEPSEEK-R1, LLAMA 3.1, AND CLAUDE 3.7 BASED ON THE GEMINI-DERIVED EVALUATION DATASET

Test Type	RAG System Using DeepSeek- R1	RAG System Using Llama 3.1	Claude 3.7
Response Relevance	%79,39	%84,41	%84,18
Response Accuracy	%30,48	%31,01	%42,18

Test Type	RAG System Using DeepSeek-R1	RAG System Using Llama 3.1	Claude 3.7
Faithfulness	%8,31	%4,73	%2,00
Factual Consistency	%18,14	%20,90	%24,92

The "A.Results Obtained with ChatGPT Based Dataset" and "B.Results Obtained with Gemini Based Dataset" sections show that the RAGAS framework was used to test the accuracy and performance of the DeepSeek-R1, Llama 3.1, and Claude 3.7 models, which are used in information retrieval-based systems. The ChatGPT and Gemini datasets were used as references. The Shapiro-Wilk Test, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank, and Friedman techniques were used to find out if these disparities in performance were statistically significant.

C. Shapiro-Wilk Test

There exist various significance tests in the literature. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test was utilized to verify the appropriate selection of these tests. This technique is employed in situations characterized by small to moderate sample sizes. This normality test checks how well the data fits a normal distribution, and the p-value tells you if the assumption that the distribution is normal is true. The normalcy assumption is not true if the p-value is less than 0.05 [27]. Below is the formula for the Shapiro-Wilk test.

$$W = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_{(i)})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (8)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are:

N: Sample size

x_i : Sorted sample values

\bar{x} : Average value of samples

a_i : Coefficients based on the expected value and covariance matrix of the normal distribution

The p value is calculated by converting the obtained W statistic to the standard normal distribution [28].

In the ChatGPT dataset, the normality assumption is generally rejected. Normality is not statistically proven for all models in the response relevance, fidelity, and factual accuracy metrics. For the Gemini dataset, the normality distribution is relatively more balanced than in the ChatGPT dataset. The response relevance measure has a normal distribution, but the assumption of normal distribution is different for other metrics. This assessment revealed that a significant percentage of the observations failed to conform to the normal distribution assumption. In this case, utilizing nonparametric tests instead of parametric analyses that follow the normal distribution assumption is a statistically solid and dependable option. Moreover, even if some measures showed a normal distribution as the observation data showed, nonparametric tests were used to make sure the methods were consistent. These nonparametric

tests give more reliable answers no matter what kind of distribution they are. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was utilized for pairwise model comparisons, whereas the Friedman Test was employed for multiple model comparisons.

D. Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

We utilized the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test to compare each statistic employed in the RAGAS framework across the three language models we were testing. This test does ranking-based analysis by looking at the size of the differences and whether they are positive or negative in pairwise comparisons [29]. The formula for the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test is shown below.

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{sgn}(d_i) \times R_i \quad (9)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are:

R_i : Absolute value difference

$\text{sgn}(d_i)$: Whether the difference is positive or negative

The Bonferroni adjustment was used to lower the chance of Type I error, which is the chance of getting false-positive findings in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test. So, the significance threshold of 0.05 equals 0.0167 [30]. The Bonferroni correction formula is shown below.

$$\alpha_{bonf} = \frac{\alpha}{m} \quad (10)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are:

α : Significance level

m: Number of models compared

95% confidence interval was used to show the test's direction and level of confidence. The confidence interval checks to see if the mean difference between the two models is positive or negative [31]. Below is the formula for the confidence interval.

$$CI = \theta \pm Z_{\alpha/2} \times SE(\theta) \quad (11)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are:

CI: Confidence interval

θ : Estimated statistics

$Z_{\alpha/2}$: Z-score for standard normal distribution

$SE(\theta)$: Standard error of the predicted value

Statistically significant differences were identified among the three models regarding the response relevance metric in the ChatGPT dataset. Analysis of the confidence intervals revealed that the Claude 3.7 model achieved superior scores compared to both Llama 3.1 and DeepSeek-R1, which are models utilized in information retrieval systems. Llama 3.1 produced inferior results compared to DeepSeek R1. The differences among the three models in the fidelity metric were statistically insignificant. The comparisons of factual accuracy between Llama 3.1 and DeepSeek R1, as well as Claude-3.7 and

DeepSeek-R1, were determined to be significant. The comparison between Claude 3.7 and Llama 3.1 did not yield statistical significance, as the p-value was greater than 0.05. All values in the response accuracy metric were statistically significant. The analysis of the confidence interval revealed that the Claude 3.7 value yielded more accurate responses compared to both Llama 3.1 and DeepSeek-R1, which were utilized in our information retrieval system.

E. Friedman Test

Models were compared pairwise utilizing the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test. This test is inadequate for comparing three or more models. Friedman tests serve to compare three or more models. This testing method is referred to as analysis of variance. This method identifies scenarios in which the differences between models are substantial [32]. The Friedman formula is presented below.

$$X_f^2 = \frac{12}{kn(k+1)} \sum_{j=1}^k R_j^2 - 3n(k+1) \quad (12)$$

Some abbreviations within the above metric are:

k: Number of models compared

n: Number of samples

R_j : j. model's rank score

$\sum_{j=1}^k R_j^2$: Sum of squares of rank scores of models

X_f^2 : Friedman test statistic

Statistical analysis reveals significant differences in performance results concerning factual accuracy, response accuracy, and response relevance. The p-values for the faithfulness metric exceeded the 0.05 threshold. No statistically significant difference exists between the models for this metric. Similar performance results are observed for the faithfulness metric.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Findings

The information retrieval models DeepSeek-R1, Llama 3.1, and Claude 3.7 exhibit distinct areas of superiority over one another. Claude 3.7 shows that ChatGPT and Gemini attained elevated scores in factual and response accuracy metrics within the evaluation datasets. Developed through contextual reasoning and varied training datasets, they generated logical responses. The attention mechanisms contributed to the consistency and knowledge-based nature of the answers in the evaluation datasets. The Llama 3.1 model demonstrated strong performance in response relevance, establishing a dependable representation regarding semantic focus and topic coherence. The DeepSeek-R1 model generates responses that are both balanced and cautious. The relatively high faithfulness score indicates a propensity for generating source-based responses. The metrics employed in the RAGAS framework exhibit partial

discrepancies in the results of the Wilcoxon and Friedman tests. The observed differences cannot be accounted for by a singular method; thus, they are assessed at various levels. The limited sample size constitutes a constraint in nonparametric tests. The limited sample size results in the rank-based Friedman test yielding conservative outcomes by minimizing variance differences, whereas the Wilcoxon test demonstrates greater sensitivity. The Bonferroni correction for the Wilcoxon test mitigates Type-I error to some degree; however, it concurrently elevates the likelihood of Type-II (false negative) error. The measure of factual accuracy, which compares Claude 3.7 and Llama 3.1, was significant prior to correction but became insignificant following correction. Within the RAGAS metric framework, a correlation exists between the metrics of response accuracy and response relevance. A high degree of response relevance is necessary for achieving response accuracy. Thus, comparable differences arise between the two metrics. The faithfulness metric quantifies the extent of interdependence between language model outputs and the reference response. The ChatGPT and Gemini datasets produced reference responses grounded in their respective contexts, resulting in comparable values for this metric across all models. The absence of semantic differences is deemed statistically plausible.

B. Limited Performance States of the System and Failure Scenarios

Information retrieval systems comprise two primary stages: the retrieval of information and the generation of responses. Failure scenarios are explained with reference to these two stages. The information retrieval process demonstrated that both ChatGPT and Gemini-based dataset evaluations produced semantically coherent answers to inquiries; however, responses were generated from documents lacking direct contextual relevance. For queries like "methods to improve system performance," the information retrieval system retrieved documents pertaining to hardware, software, and energy. The primary cause of this issue is the inadequate proficiency of embedding-based models in the Turkish language. Despite the utilization of Jina Embeddings v3, characterized by a substantial number of parameters and multilingual support, instances of incorrect matching were observed. Additionally, although the RAGAS framework demonstrated high response accuracy, there were instances of information retrieval that failed to accurately capture the correct context. Errors in the information retrieval phase stem from the strategy employed during the segmentation process. The systems engineering chatbot system was developed utilizing a fixed-length segmentation method. Some sections, in violation of information integrity, produced incomplete answers due to truncation at the beginning, middle, or end. This issue specifically resulted in decreased scores in the response accuracy metric. The system we developed produced responses that were not present in the reference document during the response generation phase. This phenomenon is referred to as hallucination. The limited context window and the fragmented nature of incoming information resulted in the system making assumptions to fill the gaps. Another situation arises when the language model, despite receiving accurate information, yields incomplete or superficial responses. The issue arises from the language model's failure to

semantically integrate incoming information or its propensity to produce brief responses when confronted with ambiguity.

VI. CONCLUSION

Recent advancements in deep learning have positioned large-scale language models as significant contributors to the domain of natural language processing. These models have demonstrated significant success in language production and comprehension. These general-purpose trained systems are recognized to have limitations in specific knowledge domains. Consequently, the fine-tuning of specific domains and the development of knowledge-based systems are gaining significance.

This study evaluated the performance of open-source, smaller-scale models in the domain of systems engineering, which necessitates expertise and technical accuracy. The DeepSeek-R1 and Llama 3.1 models possess a parameter count of 8 billion, which is relatively limited. A LoRA fine-tuning method is employed to enhance the performance of these models, utilizing a synthetically generated dataset of systems engineering questions and answers. A knowledge-retrieval-based architecture is utilized to enhance the efficiency of these models. International systems engineering documents are digitized through the Jina embedding model and stored in the Chroma vector database. Semantic and character-based search, in conjunction with ColBERT reordering methods, enhance the models' information accuracy and content consistency.

The Llama 3.1 and DeepSeek-R1 employed in information retrieval systems and Claude 3.7 models were evaluated using the RAGAS metric. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test assessed differences in binary models, while the Friedman test measured rankings in ternary models to evaluate the data from an alternative viewpoint. The evaluation results indicate that all metrics and datasets, with the exception of the faithfulness metric, demonstrated a high level of statistical significance, reflecting consistency.

The analyses in this study indicate that low-parameter open-source models can attain significant success through domain-specific development, yielding outputs that are competitive with those of commercial models. This illustrates that open-source models serve as an effective and sustainable alternative, especially in academic and industrial contexts with constrained resources. The utilization of these models yields cost savings and facilitates the development of in-house solutions for data privacy and security. The adaptable and customizable characteristics of open-source models enable institutions and researchers to develop systems that are specifically aligned with their requirements.

This study's experiments utilized a single NVIDIA A100 computing resource. Operating within a constrained infrastructure presents multiple drawbacks. The study was conducted with a limited context window due to resource constraints. The inability of language models to process extensive information in lengthy paragraphs results in incomplete answers, thereby significantly diminishing the response quality of open-source language models. Additionally, the constrained memory capacity of the hardware necessitated the selection of hyperparameter values within a limited range

during fine-tuning with the LoRA method. This constrained the model's capacity for learning. The use of a single computing resource offers the advantage of enhanced energy efficiency for low-parameter models compared to high-parameter language models in terms of hardware resource utilization. This study illustrates that numerous investigations will utilize language models in resource-limited settings, including mobile devices and personal computers.

The LoRA method demonstrates greater energy efficiency compared to full fine-tuning; however, its low-rank matrix structure may hinder effective information transfer between layers. The rank constraint limits its ability to convey contextual information, especially in complex and difficult-to-understand data sets. Furthermore, improper selection of hyperparameter values can lead to numerous issues during the learning phase. A further risk is that LoRA can rapidly learn from low-dimensional data. This process introduces data dependency. Language models may adjust to the dataset but may not perform adequately when faced with a different question sample. In the application of LoRA, a PEFT method, it is crucial to establish the appropriate hyperparameter values to address data diversity and to identify the correct rank range.

Information retrieval-based systems demonstrate efficiency in hardware-constrained environments; however, several critical issues warrant consideration. Semantic drift represents a critical challenge in RAG-based systems. The Jina embedding model utilized in this thesis is significant for vectorizing words across various languages; however, it exhibits potential for enhancement in Turkish and analogous languages. Incomplete semantic content in the segmented parts can result in semantic drift during the segmentation process. Additionally, the integration of information from various documents may lead to occasional errors in synthesis. This results from the utilization of synonyms or antonyms. A crucial consideration is that, due to the absence of real-time data, it is essential to maintain the currency of the data. Responses in RAG-based systems are generated from data stored in the vector database. It is essential to assess the currency of documents or data. Regular updates are essential for ensuring accurate and current responses.

Consequently, despite numerous limitations, advancements in open source low-parameter models yield substantial benefits across various domains, including technical proficiency, cost-effectiveness, security, customization potential, and sustainability.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

There are critical issues that need to be developed in many different application areas within the scope of large language models, fine-tuning and knowledge retrieval-based systems

The datasets created during the fine-tuning process and the documents utilized in the information retrieval systems encompass fundamental subjects in systems engineering. The main purpose is to help people who are new to systems engineering learn more about it. When creating a system engineering chatbot in the future, it would be helpful to break down systems engineering into smaller areas and make more particular datasets for each of these areas, including ones for more experienced engineers.

This study utilized two distinct datasets to evaluate model performance, yielding significant insights. Utilizing data from various domains is essential for comprehending the system's adaptability across different contexts. Currently, numerous diverse sectors exist, including healthcare, engineering, and economics, among others. Domain-specific systems created for these sectors require evaluation using the RAGAS framework. This enables the assessment of both language models and the RAGAS framework from various perspectives. Additionally, conducting these developments in various languages will enhance the analysis of language model performance regarding multilingual support.

The evaluation of systems utilizing domain-based language models exclusively within the RAGAS framework presents notable benefits; however, incorporating diverse human-based evaluation methods indicates possible enhancements to semantic assessments. Consequently, if an adequate experimental group is formed, systems utilizing domain-based information retrieval may be assessed through a hybrid evaluation approach. Additionally, alongside evaluations of the human factor and the RAGAS framework, it is advisable to conduct analyses utilizing embedding-based models.

The evaluation results are expected to be analyzed using various statistical methods, including significance testing. Evaluating the results from various perspectives will enhance the existing literature. Alongside assessing the response accuracy of information-based systems, it is crucial to evaluate the information retrieval processes at each stage to identify opportunities for optimization.

Hybrid structures in information retrieval systems can be developed through an analysis of the strengths of various models. Systems that rival commercial models can be developed by integrating the Llama 3.1 model, known for its high performance in response relevance, with the DeepSeek-R1 model, recognized for its strong faithfulness scores. Additionally, incorporating a re-evaluation process between the outputs produced by language models and the original text can enhance accuracy and contextual relevance. The elevated number of parameters within the context window and large language models enhances response quality. The values in our study were maintained at a low level due to limited infrastructure. Once the requisite infrastructure resources are established, systems designed with larger parameters and context windows may mitigate information loss and segmentation issues to some degree. Improvements can be made in the vectorization and segmentation stages to enhance the accuracy of information retrieval in RAG-based systems. The embedding models utilized for vectorization accommodate various languages; however, there is a significant deficiency of highly effective models specifically designed for Turkish. Various methods for segmenting paragraphs in documents have been developed, including semantic segmentation, character-based segmentation, page-based segmentation, and knowledge graph segmentation. Examining various segmentation strategies and assessing their accuracy in RAG-based systems would contribute significantly to the existing literature.

The low-range LoRA method was selected for the fine-tuning process due to hardware limitations. Various fine-tuning

strategies may be implemented when adequate resources are accessible. Each layer of the language model contains varying information densities. Partial and full fine-tuning can be accomplished by adjusting particular layers of the language model. The model's learning ability can be enhanced by selecting a higher rank value, which is one of the LoRA parameters. A hybrid fine-tuning method serves as a viable alternative. Hybrid fine-tuning processes combined with LoRA can enhance model performance by improving accuracy and contextual understanding. This can be achieved through parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods, including BitFit, Prefix, or Adapter Tuning. In scenarios where substantial processing power and memory capacity are accessible, a comprehensive fine-tuning approach may be contemplated for future research. Modifying the complete weight matrix of the language model enhances context representation and generalization. Furthermore, it is possible to develop language models that generate more efficient responses by minimizing semantic shifts. An additional aspect for enhancing the efficient fine-tuning process is the diversity of the training dataset. Additionally, future research should focus on identifying subfields within systems engineering and developing datasets across various domains to enhance the model's generalization capabilities. Cleaning inconsistent data and balancing English and Turkish data during the creation of training datasets will enhance model performance.

Large language models exhibit considerable potential for enhancement in the areas of security, personalization, and data privacy. Large language models possess the capacity to be driven by user input. In this context, the development of input-based and knowledge-retrieval-based security layers will represent a significant milestone. The personalization of knowledge-retrieval systems based on user data will enhance the generation of precise and high-performance responses. This method leverages historical user data and expertise to formulate response generation strategies, resulting in substantial advancements. Data utilized in knowledge-retrieval systems is universally intended for visibility to all users. Sales targets, contracts, and analogous data should not be accessible to all users. The development of role-based knowledge-retrieval systems that generate responses while maintaining confidentiality represents a significant innovation.

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